

**IMPLEMENTATION OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING
IN CREATING A PANCASILA STUDENT PROFILE AT
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Abstract: The Merdeka Curriculum is a curriculum that contains the Pancasila student profile. The main characteristics of Pancasila students include faith, devotion to God Almighty, noble morals, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical thinking and creativity. These six profiles are formed through teaching and advice in elementary school classes. The aim of orientation and teaching activities is to develop students' personalities in accordance with the unique curriculum requirements implemented at school. This article describes the implementation of orientation and counseling activities carried out at SDN 13 Parit Putus with the aim of realizing the profile of Pancasila students in elementary schools. The results of the research show that SDN 13 Parit Putus does not yet have experts in the field of guidance and advice, but the implementation of guidance and advice has been well integrated in all activities that take place in learning and at school, especially in daily habituation activities. This shows that students who become Pancasila students are able to apply Pancasila values in everyday life.

Keywords: implementation, Guidance and Counselling, Pancasila Students Profile.

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Introduction

The challenges of the 21st century have a major impact on the education sector today. Students face many challenges in predicting the ever-changing future in various fields (Kus & Aydin, 2022). Learning in this century is defined as a recognition that students not only need knowledge but also skills and attitudes to be able to compete in a diverse and technology-centered global society (Halimah & Marwati, 2022). Therefore, education in this century must be able to produce a golden generation who have attitudes and personalities that are productive, creative, innovative, and have skills that suit their individual interests and abilities (Mulyasa, 2015). As the role of education in responding to changing times becomes increasingly important, the challenges for schools as education providers also become greater and more complex. Not only does it equip students with various types of

knowledge that are developing rapidly, but it also allows the development of interests and talents, and becomes a forum for the formation of students' morals and character (Mulyasa, 2021).

Education is also a forum that discusses issues regarding the stages of implementation which initially direct a person to culture. The cultural process of improving a person's quality and dignity throughout life, which takes place in the family, school and community. Meanwhile, the quality of education is the ability of the education system, both in terms of management and the stages of education itself, which is effectively oriented towards adding value to input factors (classroom size, teachers, textbooks, situational learning and curriculum, school management, family) to obtain maximum possible results (Azmi et al., 2002).

Bearing in mind the importance of education in forming a dignified national character and civilization, making the life of the nation intelligent, developing the potential of students so that they have faith and devotion to God Almighty, and are blessed with noble morals and grow into healthy, knowledgeable, competent, creative, independent, democratic citizens. and responsible (Culture, 2003), an independent curriculum is an effort to meet all educational needs. The unique curriculum is a step towards reorganizing the Indonesian education system (Yamin & Syahrir, 2020) and is implemented to welcome change so that Indonesia can become a developed country and adapt to changing times. The independent curriculum is implemented to support the vision and mission of the President and Vice President to create a sovereign, independent and progressive Indonesia with personality based on mutual cooperation through the creation of Pancasila Students (Kemendikbud, 2020).

The Pancasila Student Profile is the main goal of the independent change curriculum, namely realizing Indonesian students as lifelong learners who are globally competent and able to reflect Pancasila values in their daily life actions. The main characteristics of Pancasila students include faith, devotion to God Almighty, noble morals, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical thinking and creativity. These six indicators reflect the 2020-2035 Indonesian Education Roadmap which is influenced by technological, social and environmental changes occurring throughout the world (Kearney, 2020). Therefore, the Pancasila student profile is an ideal target for students to reflect Pancasila values (Rusnaini, 2021).

Based on data released by SIMFONI PPA (Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of the Republic of Indonesia, Online Information System for the Protection of Women and Children). The number of perpetrators of violence based on 2023 data is very high among teenagers aged 13 to 24 years. Therefore, it is very important to bring about a mental revolution in students from an early age, from elementary school onwards. Therefore, it is very appropriate if the current curriculum focuses on character education which is based on Pancasila values and is realized in the form of a Pancasila Student Profile.

The core of developing creativity in elementary schools is competent teachers (Rahim & Hulukati, 2021). However, of course the implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in elementary schools must include not only the role of the class teacher, but also the role of the entire school community, including the principal, subject teachers and education staff. In the Pancasila student profile, students' attitudes and personalities are formed to reflect Pancasila values, so here we

teach children to understand themselves as whole humans who are able to adapt and take responsibility for their roles.

Preliminary research conducted by the author through unstructured interviews with school principals and teachers at SDN 13 Parit Putus shows that implementing counseling policies is indeed important, especially for students who experience character problems that do not reflect Pancasila values. Care and guidance services for elementary school children are not independent activities. This service program is an integral part of our efforts to improve the quality of education and develop students' attitudes and character. Therefore, guidance and advice are carried out in harmony and integration with the school's general education program. Counseling The implementation of counseling in this school is not carried out by special personnel, but involves the school principal and teachers, especially class teachers and Islamic religious education teachers. This is because the role of school staff influences the implementation of counseling activities in elementary schools (Ridwan, 2018). As a tri-center of education that also handles education, we must also include the role of family and community in this problem. The activity program is also not specifically designed, but is integrated into learning and habituation activities carried out in various school activities.

Based on the background that has been described, it can be said that the Pancasila student profile as an independent curriculum objective is related to the implementation of advisory instructions by teachers in applying character values that reflect Pancasila values. This research is limited to problems that highlight the role of counseling in implementing the Pancasila student profile at SDN 13 Parit Putus. In addition, an analysis was carried out to classify the role of guidance and advice in implementing the Pancasila student profile

Methods

This study used descriptive qualitative method. Qualitative researchers seek meaning, insight, understanding and understanding of phenomena, events or human life by engaging directly or indirectly with the contextual and comprehensive environment of the object of study (Yusuf, 2013). The focus of this research is the role of guidance and counseling in implementing the Pancasila student profile in elementary schools. The research setting was chosen with the target sample selected from a particular point of view. The following are the author's considerations in using SDN 13 Parit Putus as a research environment: (1) The school implements its own curriculum. (2) have various habit-forming activities that lead to the development of the character and profile of Pancasila students. (3) The school has a vision and mission that leads to character education that reflects the values of Pancasila. The informants were (1) the school principal, (2) Islamic religious education teacher, (3) class I-VI teacher, and (4) students' parents.

The data collection techniques used were in-depth interviews, observation and documentation. Interaction in depth with informants to gather information regarding the implementation of the advisory guidelines implemented by school principals, Islamic religious education teachers, class I to VI teachers and parents of students in implementing the Pancasila Student Profile. The observations carried out were not participatory. Observations were carried out to ascertain what kind of consultation guidance was provided by the school to develop the profile of Pancasila students. This

research documentation consists of (1) school policies, vision and mission, (2) brief identities of informants, and (3) videos and interview transcripts.

Results and Discussion

Implementation Profile Student Pancasila At SDN 13 Parit Putus Ampek Angkek District

The Pancasila Student Profile is a formula the nation's educational ideals (Irawati : 2022). The vision and mission of the Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbudristek) is to implement the Pancasila Student Profile. Pancasila Students embodies Indonesian students as lifelong learners who are globally competent and act accordingly Pancasila values. Pancasila values consists of six main characteristics: faith, devotion to God Almighty and noble morals, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical and creative.

The importance of implementing the Pancasila student profile in developing students' personalities has been proven by several studies, including research by Rusnaini et al in 2021. He found that the Pancasila student profile had an influence on students' personal formation and maintaining this goal. Appreciating the noble values and morals of our nation, becoming global citizens, achieving social justice and acquiring 21st century skills. Apart from that, the profile of Pancasila students is also students who apply Pancasila values in their entirety, which if applied consistently will influence their contribution to collective social welfare (Yudi, 2020).

The formation of the Pancasila student profile at SDN 13 Parit Putus is not only outlined in the extracurricular activities included in each class, but also in the extracurricular activities carried out at school. The Educational Unit Operational Curriculum (KOSP) of SD Negeri 13 Parit Putus consists of project-based learning that supports the implementation of increasing the profile of Pancasila students. This study is included in the co-curriculum which is created according to the main theme determined by integrating several subjects to realize the implementation project of the student profile Pancasila in education units.

Increasing the profile of Pancasila students will be carried out in two large projects which will be presented in an integrated manner starting from Grades 1, II, IV and 5. The period of this activity is separate from the period of intramural activities, so that your weekly routine activities will not be reduced. The formation of student profiles in Pancasila is closely related to the development of students' personalities which is then related to the guidance services provided by teachers. Even though advising is not a separate subject, advising is always a service provided by teachers to students. Mentoring activities are carried out with the aim of developing character values that are relevant to the formation of Pancasila student profiles.

Implementation of Activities Guidance Counseling in Implementation Student Profile Pancasila At SDN 13 Parit Putus Ampek Angkek District

The Pancasila student profile is implemented in the form of intracurricular and extracurricular activities. In implementing your own curriculum, one of the most important guidance services is understanding the personality and potential of your students (Cahyono, 2022). According to Kahyono,

guidance and advice function to help students understand, accept, guide, make decisions and implement the decisions they have taken with full responsibility. Apart from that, guidance and advice will also help students choose, utilize and maintain their potential to be more competitive and productive in the world of work in the future. Apart from that, guidance and advice also play a role in implementing the Pancasila student profile. The Pancasila Student Profile consists of six elements that students must pay attention to in their daily lives now and in the future. Pancasila Student Character is a school reference material for developing student character which not only focuses on cognitive and psychomotor aspects, but also behavioral and attitudinal aspects.

The implementation of guidance and advice at SD Negeri 13 Parit Putus has not been systematic and there are no experts in this field. However, guidance and counseling activities are included in all activities carried out in the school environment. This includes daily habituation activities that guide students to become Pancasila students who are able to apply Pancasila values in everyday life. In the learning process, the teacher simultaneously distributes material, guides and instructs students to practice behavior that reflects the Pancasila student profile. For example, in learning activities that take place in the classroom, teachers link learning content to the values of the Pancasila Profile, such as the value of diversity taught through PKN and Social Sciences subjects. Apart from teaching materials, teachers also teach attitudes that recognize the value of diversity. Apart from the learning process, teachers also provide advice and counseling outside the classroom, such as before class time in the morning, during break time, and during class time when students are still at school. If a student is found whose behavior does not match the Pancasila student profile, the teacher calls the student and provides advice and guidance regarding the student's behavior and attitudes. If there are major problems, teachers will consult with the principal if necessary, and parents of affected students will also be involved.

Guidance and counseling activities are also carried out by teachers through familiarization activities at SD Negeri 13 Parit Putus. This includes daily activities that last for 15 minutes every morning before class. The activities start from the flag raising ceremony on Monday, obligatory singing on Tuesday, Tafiz activities on Wednesday, recitation of the Asmaul Husna on Thursday, worship on Friday, and talent performances every Saturday in a different way every day. The activity organizers will rotate every week from Class IV to Class VI. The habituation activities carried out every morning are one of the school's steps in instilling the values contained in the Pancasila student profile, such as the values of faith and devotion to God Almighty which are realized through habituation to religious activities. There are also values of diversity which are realized through flag ceremonies every Monday morning, as well as values of creativity and independence which are realized through student warm-up activities every morning.

In the administrative sector, the implementation of guidance and counseling at SDN 13 Parit Putus is still not well documented. Apart from that, class teachers do not create special learning programs that are implemented in a structured manner like other class learning management systems. The simple support and advice provided is that each class teacher records important events in each class in a notebook. This memo is a report from the teacher to the principal, usually presented at a teacher council meeting, and is the basis for decision making in choosing the right treatment. The guidance and advice contained in this book is aimed not only at students who have problems, but also at capable students, such as teachers who provide guidance and advice to help students who have

potential in certain fields to further develop their potential in the future. Apart from special notes regarding problems and events that require guidance and advice, teachers also make notes regarding the characteristics of good students which are associated with the Pancasila Student Profile. This notebook can also be a reference for teachers and school principals when providing guidance and advice to students.

To overcome various problems identified by teachers and provide appropriate guidance and counseling services, teachers use various techniques to identify and understand students, such as: First: Evaluation during the semester. This test refers to the guidance and advice provided by teachers regarding cognitive problems such as learning difficulties, creativity problems, and critical thinking abilities, which represent the requirements of the Pancasila Profile. This test allows teachers to identify students' skills and develop strategies to provide appropriate guidance and counseling services to help students master those skills. Second, we conducted teacher-led observations to observe students' daily attitudes and behavior during class hours, both in learning activities in the classroom and outside the classroom. Through observation, teachers can identify students' strengths and weaknesses, especially in terms of students' emotional and psychomotor abilities.

The results of observations can also be used by teachers to develop appropriate teaching and counseling strategies to overcome various problems such as: B. Aspects of the Pancasila student profile, namely noble morals, mutual cooperation, independence and other attitudes that are reflected in students' daily behavior at school. Third, the teacher uses interview techniques. This technique is usually used by teachers to explore students' personal and personal problems. Interviews conducted by teachers to investigate student problems aim to understand student problems as a whole and develop appropriate teaching and counseling strategies to overcome these problems. If necessary, teachers can also interview colleagues, other teachers, and parents.

An example of a problem related to the Pancasila student profile that requires the provision of guidance and counseling services and requires an interview to understand it is the problem of mutual cooperation. Students often have no contact with friends and prefer to be alone in class. This requires personal support through interviews, where the teacher interviews the affected students in a relaxed manner while talking to them. Teachers can invite students to chat about their friends in class to convince the teacher that this is what causes students not to want to hang out with their friends. You can also interview classmates and parents at home to get a sense of the student's personality, such as whether they prefer not to have social contact or only want to interact within the school environment.

The application of guidance and advice is very important in elementary schools because many elementary school students experience problems in participating in learning, and these problems exist both for themselves and the people around them (Batbara, 2018). Career guidance in elementary schools is about providing specialized teaching to help students develop a passion for learning (Widada, 2013) and enable them to solve the problems they face, including those related to developmental challenges (Saidah, 2017). Additionally, counseling services play an important role in meeting students' social and emotional needs (Springer, 2020) as well as academic and professional needs (Scott, at all, 2016). However, evidence from primary schools shows that there are several deficiencies in guidance and counseling services, such as a lack of professional staff and infrastructure and equipment problems (Hatunoglu, 2021). Counseling in elementary schools is very necessary for

students to plan a better life in the future (Evi, 2020), especially after the pandemic which affected students' mental health and behavior (London & Ingram, 2018; Talmus, 2019)..

Conclusion

Counseling at SD Negeri 13 Parit Putus helps students develop personalities that suit the Pancasila student profile. It covers six aspects. SD Negeri 13 Parit Putus and devotion to God Almighty, noble morals, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical and creative thinking, and in the future students will have the spirit of Pancasila

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